

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE POLICY AND ANIMAL NUTRITION CASE OF DR ECKEL ANIMAL NUTRITION IN NIEDERZISSEN, GERMANY

Mushimiyimana Diane*

Mount Kenya University, Nairobi, Kenya

Eugenia Nkechi Irechukwu

Mount Kigali University, Kigali, Rwanda

* Corresponding Author

ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to analyze the impact of artificial intelligence on animal feeding policy, with a specific focus on, case study of Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company. The goal is to assess how an AI policy impacts automated milking, health monitoring, the food supply chain, and feed quality in the company. The study uses descriptive and correlational research designs, based on theories like the theory of constraints and the theory of change. Data collection involved surveying 138 community project groups and 24 specialists, with analysis using descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and content analysis. The results show a positive relationship between AI policy and quality improvement in the dairy market, indicating significant support for food development. Additionally, the study reveals a connection between health policy and livestock development and the impact of AI policy on intellectual property rights in the food industry and livestock production. Finally, the implementation of AI policy demonstrates a clear link to progress in animal nutrition, particularly in terms of blockchain technology's influence on price prediction and animal development. These findings highlight the transformative potential of AI in enhancing animal nutrition and driving positive changes in the industry.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), AI Policy and Animal Nutrition, Animal Nutrition Company, Animal feed, Feed supplier inquiries.

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1. BACKGROUND

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in various sectors has led to significant advancements, and animal nutrition is no exception. Recent studies have highlighted the positive impact of AI on animal welfare, feed quality, and livestock management. AI technologies have shown great promise in improving animal health monitoring and welfare. Giraudoux et al. (2022) emphasize that AI can integrate human, animal, and environmental health to support sustainable farming practices. This comprehensive approach, known as One Health or Eco Health, recognizes the importance of addressing physical health, mental well-being, and natural behavior collectively ^{1,2}.

By incorporating sensor technology and AI in animal husbandry, real-time data collection on health parameters is enabled, allowing for quicker interventions and improved management practices. Eckel (2018) states that sensors help collect data on various aspects of cows, such as udder health, cow comfort, prevention of lameness, observation of social behavior, and metabolism management. AI's role in automated milking systems has revolutionized the dairy industry by enhancing efficiency and ensuring the well-being of dairy cows. Holmstrom and Beckham (2017) note that AI-equipped robots with sensors and cameras provide continuous monitoring of cattle, enabling early detection of diseases and abnormalities, leading to proactive health management and reduced health risks. Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition GmbH & Co. KG has been a pioneer in integrating AI into its operations, focusing on innovative feed additives that combine efficiency, sustainability, and animal welfare. Their products aim to improve feed quality, enhance lung function in livestock, and reduce the need for medications through natural solutions like essential oils and plant extracts ^{3,4}.

Furthermore, the application of AI in the food supply chain has significant implications for animal nutrition. Doyle (2016) highlights how AI algorithms can optimize feeding processes by creating personalized nutrition plans based on data analysis of animal behavior, milk production, and nutritional needs. This precision feeding not only improves animal health and milk yield but also minimizes resource wastage and environmental impact. The incorporation of AI in animal nutrition aligns with ethical considerations and regulatory frameworks. As technology advances, it is crucial to ensure responsible use, balancing innovation with ethics and social equity. This approach can create a harmonious coexistence of technology, animals, and humans, fostering a sustainable future for agriculture. The integration of AI in animal nutrition offers numerous opportunities for enhancing animal welfare, optimizing feed quality, and ensuring sustainable farming practices. Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition GmbH & Co. KG serves as a prime example of successful AI integration in enhancing animal nutrition and promoting innovative solutions. As AI technologies continue to evolve, they hold the potential to drive significant positive changes in the animal nutrition industry, contributing to the overall well-being of livestock and the sustainability of agricultural practices ⁵⁻⁷.

The main goal of this research is to thoroughly investigate the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in animal nutrition, with a focus on the innovative approaches taken by Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition GmbH & Co. KG in Niederzissen, Germany. The study aims to shed light on how AI technologies are transforming animal nutrition by improving feed quality, animal health, and farm management. Additionally, the research seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of groundbreaking feed additives developed by Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition in enhancing livestock performance and sustainability. Moreover, it aims to address the regulatory and ethical considerations surrounding the use of AI in animal nutrition to ensure responsible and sustainable practices. Ultimately, this study aspires to contribute to a deeper understanding of how AI can revolutionize agriculture, specifically in animal nutrition, and provide practical insights and recommendations based on empirical evidence and case studies.

By accomplishing these objectives, the research aims to illuminate both the advantages and challenges of incorporating AI into animal nutrition, thus offering valuable insights for researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to drive sustainable and ethical progress in the agricultural sector ^{6,8,9}.

Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition GmbH & Co. KG company

The researcher is interested in artificial intelligence (AI). It since the digital revolution brought about by the internet and digital technologies, perhaps the most important change of our industrial age is artificial intelligence, although it is the next change ¹⁰. Artificial intelligence has many applications in various industries ¹¹. International Data Corporation predicts that artificial intelligence solutions will generate more than \$100 billion in revenue by 2025, and artificial intelligence revenues will reach \$47 billion in 2016, whereas major technology ¹², companies worldwide have spent approximately \$30 billion on artificial intelligence.

Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition GmbH & Co. KG (Fig.1) is one of the leading international suppliers of modern feed additives and solutions that improve animal nutrition ¹³. Top products as well as targeted research and development make the company a preferred partner in the compound feed industry and in agriculture. Its portfolio includes its own high-quality products as well as select products from international manufacturers.

Fig. 1 Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition GmbH & Co. KG company

Since its inception nearly 25 years ago, the company has successfully developed dynamic and innovative solutions for animal nutrition. Innovative feed additives, which uniquely combine efficiency, sustainability and animal welfare, make Dr. Eckel a pioneer of global animal nutrition ¹⁴. The creative solutions promote healthy animals, profitable production and overarching responsibility. Hence, innovation focuses on highly topical issues related to animal nutrition, such as feed hygiene, food safety, resource efficiency and animal welfare. Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition operates in Germany and in more than 40 other countries, generating €20 million in revenue.

Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition is all about innovative feed additives made in Germany. Their value-orientated family business was founded by Dr Antje Eckel in Niederzissen ¹⁵, in the beautiful Eifel region, in 1994, where they are still firmly established. They have meanwhile gained international success. Indeed, Dr. Eckel is one of the world's foremost companies in the sector with a specific focus on animal welfare, developing products that make animal nutrition more resource-efficient, climate-friendly and healthy ¹⁶.

This is how they contribute to sustainable global nutrition. Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition represents excellence, innovation and responsibility towards people, animals and the environment¹⁷. Our products combine innovation and quality, which is what sets them apart. The customers value their solutions for profitable animal nutrition¹⁸. These promote animal welfare and enable our customers to achieve sustainable, long-term success. To this end, they multinational team of experts conducts research and works with specialists from around 20 different countries. This is but one of the reasons why Dr. Eckel was identified as a hidden champion by the Forschungszentrum Mittelstand (FZM), a research institute for the German Mittelstand at the University of Trier. Every year, they invest more than 10 per cent of their revenue in innovation projects for the customers, partners and employees. These consist of new products, consolidating their digital infrastructure and sustainability projects such as replacing the current company fleet with electric vehicles, among others¹⁹. And their commitment is paying off, as evidenced by the various awards they receive, including Leading Employer, TOP 100 Innovator and the 'Innovative through Research' seal of approval²⁰⁻²².

Artificial Intelligence policy for health monitoring

Artificial intelligence (AI) is important for dairy monitoring and management. By collecting and analyzing large amounts of data, AI algorithms can monitor each cow's health, fertility, diet, and milk production²³. Farmers can work to keep the cows healthy and increase milk production by detecting abnormalities or early signs of disease to prevent problems from occurring. The goal is to create a future where technology and humanity work hand in hand to create a more sustainable, ethical, and prosperous agricultural sector,²⁴. A future where we harness the power of AI and sensors to enhance the welfare of animals, while also respecting the rights and needs of farmers and consumers. To collaborate effectively with AI, farmers need to apply their knowledge of livestock and the environment to advance technology. Artificial Intelligence and IoT in Dairy Farm. The undeniable potential of AI and sensor technologies to enhance animal welfare in livestock farming is evident. This research explores how to measure animal welfare, focusing on the farmer's perspective ethical and societal impact. It helps connect advanced technology with the people affects, creating new innovative perspective. Integrating AI and sensor technologies in agriculture introducing new tools. It represents a change in how we farm. It involves a fusion through generations of farmers with cutting-edge advancements of the modern era²⁵. Using technology and our knowledge of animals, we can build a stronger connection thru livestock. Rather than merely striving to boost production, our primary focus should lie in nurturing their well-being. Together, through this compassionate approach, we can elevate our relationship with livestock to new heights.

Effect of an Artificial Intelligence policy in automated milking on animal nutrition

Globally, in developed countries, automatic milking technology represents a significant application of artificial intelligence in the dairy industry²⁴. This technology utilizes measurement tools and data analysis to tackle environmental issues, optimize resource utilization, and improve animal welfare. By using advanced technologies like environmental sensors and imaging, we can accurately assess and enhance animal welfare in livestock farming. This will help animals and make the industry more sustainable and ethical. Thousands of dairy cows produce their valuable milk every day²⁵. However, this can only be achieved by maintaining the health and well-being of the cows in the long run. In the case of dairy cows, better animal welfare directly correlates with improved health and performance. The following factors are crucial for ensuring the welfare of dairy cows: udder health, cow comfort, lameness, and social behavior are key factors. Maintaining health helps prevent economic losses and improve performance.

The somatic cell count is an important indicator of udder health. Providing comfortable rest areas and preventing injuries is important. Addressing hoof injuries and diseases is crucial to prevent lameness. Meeting the social needs of cows is important for their well-being.

2. RESULTS

This section presents the research findings and discussions on project management practices and the sustainability of agricultural projects, using Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company as a case study. The data was collected from 138 beneficiaries and 24 key informants. The information includes demographic details, and the results are analyzed based on the specific objectives of the study and various topics. Experience with technology also plays a crucial role. A farmer's values and beliefs about animal welfare, sustainability, and traditional farming methods can affect how open they are to using new technology. As for farm-related factors, the characteristics of a farm can strongly influence the feasibility and appeal of technology adoption. Farm size, livestock type, financial resources, and labor availability are all important factors when deciding whether to use a technology on a farm. Geographical location also matters, as it can affect access to technology and related support services. In addition, the characteristics of the technology itself are pivotal to its acceptance. The perceived usefulness and ease of use are key factors in technology adoption. The cost of the technology and the expected return on investment also hold sway over the decision-making process. Moreover, the compatibility of the technology with existing practices, equipment, and infrastructure can significantly impact its adoption.

Respondents Findings

Generally, the study examined participants' gender, age, education, marital status, and years working at Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company (Detailed in Fig. 2). This examination aims to determine if these factors influence their opinions and perspectives.

Fig. 2 Gender Profile (Source: Primary Data, 2023)

The research results show that 73.2% of the families studied are female and 26.6% are male. Most of the interviewees were women working in the animal feed industry and were therefore selected as beneficiaries of Rwanda's animal feed AI policy: a case Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company.

The findings in Fig. 3 show that the respondents were in the 45-54 age group (40.2%), while a small number of respondents (7.6%) were in the 25-35 age group. This means that many older adults are less likely to benefit from the program because it helps them.

Fig. 3 Age of Respondents (Source: Primary Data, 2023)

Educational profile of Respondents

The results of the proficiency level show that many people benefit of Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company the success is important because of the knowledge gained. Therefore, the information is shown in the Fig.4.

Fig. 4 Monitoring Education (Source: Primary Data, 2023)

The findings pertaining to the education level of participants hold great significance in evaluating the interplay between education, artificial intelligence policy, and animal nutrition, specifically within the context of Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company. The results emphasize that a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between these factors is crucial. The study uncovers various insights into the impact of artificial intelligence policy on animal nutrition at Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company, highlighting specific objectives and variables (Fig. 5). These objectives encompass the evaluation of AI policy pertaining to automated milking and animal nutrition, the establishment of AI policy for health monitoring, the determination of AI's role in the food supply chain, and the examination of AI's contribution to enhancing feed quality and animal nutrition within the company.

By employing descriptive statistics, the research seeks to analyze the independence and fluctuations within these variables, with a specific focus on gauging whether animal nutrition has witnessed improvements in the framework of Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company. The evaluation utilizes key metrics such as quality enhancement, increased quantity, and heightened customer satisfaction to assess the outcomes and effectiveness of animal nutrition practices.

Fig. 5 AI policy to improve food quality and animal nutrition

Artificial Intelligence Policy for Health Monitoring and Animal Nutrition

Artificial Intelligence policy in automated milking and animal nutrition. This study does not contradict the study of Young (2019), which shows that automatic milking machine can work well when creating smart farm (SDF), which is an important concept that can meet the demand for good dairy products. Moreover, Donepudi (2016) Due to the increase in the world population, the demand for dairy products is increasing day by day. According to previous data, countries producing milk and dairy products are more than developed countries, but this ratio will expand further as the world population increases and the diet changes. Almost 80% of dairy products in underdeveloped countries come from small farmers. These small and family farmers have moved away from mechanization and traditional agriculture. These technologies need to be used to meet the needs of the growing world. Donepudi (2017) in this new economic world, farmers face many problems such as livestock management, sustainability and expensive farming. Facing these limitations and problems, farmers can become more efficient and productive by improving production, controlling animals to prevent diseases, controlling health problems, and increasing milk production. The table below provides a relative analysis of different studies in dairy farming.

Artificial Intelligence Policy for Health Monitoring and Animal Nutrition

Holmstrom and Beckham (2017) Artificial intelligence robots equipped with sensors and cameras are revolutionizing cattle care. A machine that monitors the health, behavior and well-being of cattle. Information obtained by analyzing intelligent algorithms to ensure early detection of disease, illness or bad behavior. By informing farmers quickly, they can ensure animal health and prevent health risks.

Robotic cattle monitoring systems provide continuous monitoring, allowing farmers to better manage their animals. Fokoué (2019) Artificial intelligence (AI) involves many theories and techniques to solve problems of high demand or algorithmic complexity. It spans many disciplines, including mechanical engineering, software engineering, data science, and statistics (Figure 1). Many artificial intelligence methods were proposed in the 1950s and have been improved or expanded in recent years with the increase in computer power. Recent developments are the result of the interaction of many data from different sources, especially health data, as well as data from other disciplines such as artificial intelligence and biomedicine. For Holmstrom and Beckham (2017), the challenge for animal health managers is to determine how to implement management based on specific, local conditions (e.g., characteristics of the farm, results of the mission) and area (e.g., wealth, location of the farm, management priorities). They should expect to influence health, environmental and management changes and provide good health advice. Questions remain about how to foster innovation in AD, such as predicting the properties needed for candidate molecules in vaccine strategies or drug delivery, or measuring interaction by taking advantage of new technologies (such as genomic selection of resistant animals, new vaccines) over traditional technologies. Hur et al (2019) recent studies have focused on using artificial intelligence or business intelligence to integrate people and their decisions through effective management and adaptive strategies. One of the challenges is to maintain clear and appropriate rules for particular situations. These studies have just begun in AD and must be expanded as part of agroecological development, meeting the needs of existing society for good products, respecting ecosystems and their biodiversity on the one hand, and taking into account the hands of animals on the other. Health and justice, and global health security more broadly.

Artificial Intelligence Policy in Food Supply Chain and Animal Nutrition

Globally, in Europe, a research done by Doyle (2016) Artificial intelligence optimizes the baby's feeding process thanks to proper nutrition. Artificial intelligence algorithms can create personalized feeding plans for each cow by analyzing data on cow behavior, milk production and nutrition. This unique technology ensures that each cow receives the best nutrition, increasing milk production and the overall health of the animal. Precision feeding also prevents overfeeding and wasted resources, thus reducing waste and the environment.

Water is an essential nutrient for all animals, Kamilaris, et al (2016). Access to good water is essential for the health and well-being of cattle. Milk contains approximately 87% water. Water use is closely related to environmental factors such as milk production, food moisture, weather, temperature and humidity. This project includes a blanket and a heated pool that can be filled with water from a high-pressure line. The float valve controls the balance of water in the tank.

Lynn (2019) The complexity arises from many different factors, such as the perishable nature of products, high demand fluctuations due to increased demand for different products in different seasons, and increased user experience in production safety, quality and environmental issues. When discussing the integration of AI, the knowledge of different stakeholders in the product is important. It is important to ensure that stakeholders understand how AI works, as they are the ones who ensure the smooth functioning of the supply chain. Ten applications were found to be running at three levels: high, medium and low, while two applications were found to be running at medium and low levels.

Maclachlan et al (2017) conducted a literature review to capture and collect information Many AI applications from all areas of SC. Most of the scientific results of artificial intelligence applications arise from the use of water in agricultural products.

When the data is examined, it can be seen that the areas where the least research have been done on Many AI applications from all areas of SC. Most of the scientific results of artificial intelligence applications arise from the use of water in agricultural products. When the data is examined, it can be seen that the areas where the least research has been done on the use of artificial intelligence in agricultural products are the areas where technology is low. The downstream of SC includes export business, e-commerce, food safety, equipment etc. Contains.

Artificial Intelligence Policy in Feeding Quality and Animal Nutrition

Globally, In Europe, a research done by Morand et al (2020) Quality control in the dairy industry is crucial to ensure the quality of milk. AI-driven solutions help maintain quality by analyzing the formula. Machine learning algorithms can analyze the composition of milk, diagnose diseases and detect inefficiencies that may affect the quality of milk. By quickly identifying and fixing problems, farmers can prevent bad products from entering the market. AI-based management solutions increase consumer confidence and protect the reputation of dairy products. India's National AI for Animal Policy aims to increase animal productivity and sustainable production while protecting the environment, preserving animal biodiversity, ensuring biosecurity and enabling people to farm for a living. For example, the study published in calculating the needs of the United States. (Sustainable Precision Animal Nutrition Analysis). The problem is that the integration of all this information will be important in the development of holistic animal nutrition. Number of interactions with other animals. Variability of components. Starch 1 is considered insoluble because the starch surrounding the tissue prevents digested starch reaching the starch. Starch 2 is a naturally occurring starch that is resistant to digestion due to its granular structure. Condensed starch is formed when starch granules are heated and cooled, thus creating a new crystal matrix that is resistant to enzymatic hydrolysis.

How Artificial Intelligence (AI) is Transmuting Animal Nutrition and Health.

What is the relationship of artificial intelligence to animal nutrition and health, are there any applications for artificial intelligence in animal nutrition? As technology continues to advance, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is playing an increasingly significant role in transforming various industries. One area where AI is making a profound impact is in the fields of animal nutrition and health. This explores the key applications of AI in these fields and the transformative effects it is having on animal well-being. AI Applications in Animal Nutrition. Automated Feeding Systems and Precision Nutrition equipped with AI technology are revolutionizing the way animals are fed. For example, innovative solutions like Real Appetite AI have been developed to reduce food waste and ensure that animals eat an appropriate amount of feed intake. Drones are also being utilized to track environmental changes and ensure optimal feeding conditions, thus contributing to precision nutrition for animals. Data-Driven Diet Optimization and Formulation, the use of AI in animal nutrition includes harnessing the power of data to optimize and formulate animal diets using mechanistic software. By combining data from various sources such as animal health records, environmental data, and historical disease information (besides other resources as well), AI can help in creating tailored and optimized diets for different animal species. This data-driven approach ensures that animals receive precise and balanced nutrition for optimal health and growth.

Monitoring Feeding Behaviours Using AI Technology

Currently, AI technologies are enabling the monitoring of individual animal feeding behaviours with a high level of accuracy. These technologies automate the tracking of feeding behaviours, including the time spent near feeding troughs, feeding frequency, and feed intake and other additional feeding behaviours.

Such detailed monitoring allows for the early detection of changes in feeding patterns, which can be indicative of health issues or nutrition issues, and thus assists in taking corrective action to solve this issue. M. I. (2016) Agri-IoT, with the recent advancement of the Internet of Things (IoT), it is now possible to process a large number of sensor data streams using different large-scale IoT platforms. These IoT frameworks are used to collect, process and analyse data streams in real-time and facilitate the provision of smart solutions designed to provide decision support. Existing IoT-based solutions are mainly domain-dependent, providing stream processing and analytics focusing on specific areas (smart cities, healthcare etc.). In the context of agri-food industry, a variety of external parameters belonging to different domains (e.g. weather conditions, regulations etc.) have a major influence over the food supply chain, while flexible and adaptive IoT frameworks, essential to truly realize the concept of smart farming, are currently inexistent. Dr. Eckel (2009), Disease Prevention through leveraging AI approaches in animal health makes it possible to address highly complex issues such as disease detection and prevention. Hur B, Hardefeldt LY, Verspoor K, Baldwin T, Gilkerson JR (2019) Antimicrobial Resistance is a global crisis that veterinarians contribute to through their use of antimicrobials in animals. Antimicrobial stewardship has been shown to be an effective means to reduce antimicrobial resistance in hospital environments. Effective monitoring of antimicrobial usage patterns is an essential part of antimicrobial stewardship and is critical in reducing the development of antimicrobial resistance. AI-driven predictive analytics are revolutionizing animal health management by analysing historical health data, genetic information, and environmental factors. This facilitates the early detection of diseases and potential health issues, allowing for timely intervention and preventive measures. Remote Monitoring and Early Diagnosis of Health Issues. AI-powered technologies are transforming the way animal health is monitored and diagnosed. Through remote monitoring and advanced data analytics, farm managers and animal health professionals can gain real-time insights into the health status of animals. This allows for the early diagnosis of health issues, even in large-scale farming operations, and enables timely intervention to prevent the spread of diseases and ensure the well-being of animals. The integration of AI into animal nutrition and health is reshaping the way animals are cared for and managed. The use of AI in precision nutrition, automated feeding systems, and disease management is enhancing the well-being of animals and improving the efficiency of animal farming practices. However, challenges such as data privacy, ethical considerations, and the need for skilled professionals to manage AI systems remain. Despite these challenges, the potential for AI to continue transforming animal nutrition and health is vast, and ongoing research and innovation in this area will be crucial for realizing its full benefits. AI has the potential to revolutionize animal nutrition and health, and its applications continue to expand and evolve rapidly. We should keep pace with these updates and changes in the current world, and at the present time, to obtain better results and to maximize productivity, profitability, and environmental sustainability. As our understanding of AI and its capabilities grows, the future of animal well-being looks increasingly promising.

3. DISCUSSION

This research investigates the impact of AI policy on animal nutrition, focusing on specific objectives such as evaluating AI policy in automated milking and animal nutrition. It aims to establish an Artificial Intelligence policy for health monitoring and animal nutrition, assess AI policy in the food supply chain, and examine AI policy and animal nutrition in various countries. Additionally, the research explores the role of Artificial Intelligence policy in improving feed quality and overall animal nutrition.

Artificial Intelligence policy in automated milking and animal nutrition

The study assessed the effect of Artificial Intelligence policy in automated milking and animal nutrition at Dr. Eckel Animal Nutrition Company. Results demonstrated that 50% strongly agree with the Milk booth. Giving farmers access to the best bull genetics in the world, 36.6% agree that smart sensors, Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things and sensor technology have created the future of work. Livestock exports help improve safety and efficiency, according to dairy analysis; 40.2% of AI techniques can be used to monitor the compatibility of dairy products, and improve the working environment of dairy products. Additionally, 37.3% agreed that milk quality and abnormalities are symptoms of climate change, such as global warming and climate change. This is important because a significance level < 0.05 indicates that the change in milk supports a positive development. However, analysis of milk showed positive correlation with quantity improvement ($r = 0.121$, p -value = 0.044) and consumer improvement ($r = 0.102$, p -value = 0.091). Correlation was established by analysis of dairy and consumer development ($r = 0.119$, p -value = 0.048) and the association between breast milk quality and improved symptoms and expenses (0.512, p -value = 0.036). Milk performance and quality improvement, customer development with negative signs ($r = 0.546$, p -value = 0.023)

According to the significance of different models, the above correlations are significant and the sign of the difference is greater than 0.05. Change is achieved by improving quality, increasing quantity and improving customer service and vice versa. Artificial Intelligence Policy for Health Monitoring and Animal Nutrition. Artificial intelligence policy for health care and advanced animal nutrition. These findings indicate that temperature is an important factor in determining growth in beef cattle. In this context, 46.0% agree with Calvin. Start preparing for breeding season using artificial intelligence (AI) and natural resources. 31.2% agreed that eating can be made faster by walking and separating food correctly. AI machines can use advanced X-ray machines, cameras and lasers to sort food by size, color and weight. The results show the relationship between matrices. Wisdom policy for improving health care and animal nutrition considers detection of heat to be associated with quality improvement (0.176). However, calving correlated with improved quality at 0.845% and improved quantity at 0.874%. The results showed that room changes at estrus detection led to a 9.1% improvement in animal nutrition, calving led to a 19.2% change in animal nutrition, led to a 3.4% change in animal feed during the measurement period, resulting in a 9.1% improvement in animal nutrition. Hence, other results showed that it led to a 3.4% change in eating and drinking. It led to a 3.4% change in animal nutrition, and it leads to a 3.4% to 5.6% improvement in food production.

Artificial Intelligence Policy in Food Supply Chain and Animal Nutrition

The third research objective illustrates the AI policy to improve livestock production in the food industry. According to the survey results, 34.1% of respondents agreed to send alerts to farmers to provide immediate information on crops. In addition, 30.8% of people are dissatisfied with bulls' behavior and argue that semen collected from bulls is analyzed to prevent diseases that bulls can transmit to cows during birth. This study establishes the relationship between intellectual property rights related to food and animal nutrition. The Pearson correlation coefficient between notification to farmers and quality improvement is $r = 0.843$. The ratio of messages sent to farmers to the number of improvements is 0.871, and the ratio of messages sent to farmers and customers to improved corrections is 957. This means that there is a good relationship between the variables. When these elements are created, each of them has a positive effect on the development of the animal. The results showed an improvement in animal nutrition of 0.25 and the coefficient per unit change in yield was limited to 0.97.

Artificial Intelligence Policy in Feeding Quality and Animal Nutrition

Artificial intelligence sets rules to improve food quality and animal nutrition. The research found that 46.0% of people agreed that blockchain AI creates systems using technology to help people and make decisions. Blockchain is primarily a financial document that can provide security, transparency and proof. 31.2% of Participants acknowledge that AI has applications at all stages of the policy cycle, from the planning process to policy making, decision-making, implementation and evaluation, and that computer vision allows them to monitor, analyze and determine their responses. While electronic devices can track individual animals' food, improve resource use, increase efficiency and increase efficiency, 37.3% agree to help people and make high decisions, blockchain technology is a distributed ledger. Application proof. The results show a positive relationship between intellectual property and livestock production. The findings reveal that the correlation between block chain chains is 0.176, and the increase in prediction is connected to the increase in quantity. The results showed that the change in block chain led to the improvement of livestock by 9.1%, while the change of owner led to the improvement of livestock by 19.2%.

4. CONCLUSION

The researcher presents the study results on how ownership influences animal nutrition, which includes the use of sensors for milk testing. An analysis has found a positive correlation between changes in milk and animal growth. Monitoring with technology like X-ray scanners improves animal health. Health policies have a crucial impact on the economics of livestock. Intellectual property plays a crucial role in ensuring the safety of food and in monitoring cattle. The correlation between farmer notifications and quality enhancement is $r = 0.843$. Regional initiatives are playing a crucial role in enhancing animal nutrition. Integrating blockchain with AI improves the quality of animal food, demonstrating a clear correlation with the development of the livestock industry.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations can be drawn: The insights and indicators highlighted in this research will enable companies to assess the value and necessity of developing or acquiring artificial intelligence. Through business analysis, stakeholders can pinpoint areas where AI is most suitable. For managers, this can assist in devising long-term strategies for intellectual property development. Furthermore, the researchers suggest that those involved in animal research explore new artificial intelligence tools and explore areas where current AI applications fail to provide additional value and incur extra costs. Additionally, crafting investment strategies will help businesses prepare for the integration of AI and achieve success. In addition to AI applications, investment advice should also encompass investing in the right workforce, providing training, and hiring experts to support the adoption and management of AI systems. The agricultural and livestock sectors, owing to their research, capital, higher education, and infrastructure, possess the greatest advantage in combining skills. Thus, this study proposes that government agencies implement specific policies to encourage large agricultural companies to engage in knowledge sharing and support skill development. Armed with this knowledge, agricultural companies are advised to focus on integrating intelligent technology in the downstream part of the supply chain (SC) and aim to generate profits through its application. Consequently, researchers must delve deeper into SC's accounting expertise.

Future studies should focus on more empirical research to support AI policies. Use survey data from each installation to inform AI policy settings. The data can help identify the needs of the new construction site and suggest ways to improve the proposed classification. The study suggests conducting similar research in other countries and regions to accurately represent the situation in the area. The results will guide the government's development policy.

6. DECLARATIONS

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The authors declare that no fund was received for this research.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to the best of our knowledge.

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate

Not applicable

Availability of Data and Material/ Data Access Statement

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Authors Contributions

Mushimiyimana Diane: Conceptualization, writing and editing.

Eugenia Nkechi Irechukwu: Supervision, revision, and editing.

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